

VISCOSITY OF NON-IDEAL BINARY LIQUID SYSTEMS.

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An equation on the lines of Kendall and Munroe's cube root equation has been proposed and shown to work as satisfactorily as other equations on eleven binary liquid systems whose η - c curves either sag or show maxima or minima

Various equations have been proposed from time to time expressing the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures as a function of composition, e.g., the cube root equation; $\eta^{\frac{1}{3}} = \eta_1^{\frac{1}{3}}x_1 + \eta_2^{\frac{1}{3}}x_2$, (Kendall and Munroe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 1787) and the equations of Macleod (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, **19**, 17) and Spells (*ibid.*, 1936, **32**, 530). The cube root equation represents some ideal systems quite satisfactorily but fails in the case of some others. It was thought desirable to see, if by taking into account the variations of density that occur on mixing two liquids, the cube root equation may not be made to represent the viscosity of non-ideal liquid mixtures such as those whose η - c curves show maxima, minima, etc. Of the various modifications tried, the following form was found to meet with some success :

$$\eta^{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{\rho_0}{100} \left(\eta_1^{\frac{1}{3}}v_1 + \eta_2^{\frac{1}{3}}v_2 \right) \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_c} \right)^m$$

where η , η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of the mixture and pure components, v_1 and v_2 , volumes of the pure components in 100 grams of the mixture, ρ_0 , the observed density of the mixture, ρ_c , the density calculated from the

formula $\frac{100}{v_1 + v_2}$, and m , a constant. The results are summarised in the

following table for eleven mixtures. The data for the first five mixtures were obtained from the work of Dunstan and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1728), for 6 and 7 from Baker's paper (*ibid.*, 1912, **101**, 1409, for 8 and 9 from Bramley's (*ibid.*, 1916, **109**, 10) for 10 from Macleod's (*loc. cit.*) and for the last from Srinivasan and Prasads' paper (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **34**, 1139).

TABLE I.

Mixture.	Nature of curve.	Value of m .	Percentage deviation.	
			Present equation.	Macleod' equations (where known).
Picoline-water	Maximum	13.5	14.8	9.1
Pyridine-water	"	16	9.9	5.4
Lutidine-ethyl alcohol	Maximum and minimum	2.5	1.7	2.06
Pyridine-benzene	Almost linear	4.5	2.8	
Pyridine-ethyl alcohol	Minimum	-3.4	3.9	
Methyl alcohol-ethyl ether	Very slight sag	1	4.8	
Ethyl alcohol-phenetole	Minimum	-18	4.2	
Phenol-aniline	Maximum	24	10	
Phenol-acetone	Indefinite	-18.5	5.3	
Ethyl alcohol-water	Maximum	9	18.0	18.8
Acetic acid-water	"	5	21.4	16*

It may be seen from the last two columns that the deviations in the present case are generally of the same order as in Macleod's two constant equation. It would appear thus that the factor $\left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_c}\right)^m$ accounts at least in

some measure, for the changes in volume or field of force surrounding the molecules, which are the causes for effecting non-ideal conditions. The rather high values for ' m ' in some cases may not be surprising when one considers that even for pure liquids, the forces of attraction between the centres of molecules vary inversely as the eighth power (at least) of their distance (Edser, *Fourth Report of Colloid Chemistry*, D.S.I.R., 1922; Newton Friend, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **34**, 813). However, it is not possible to attach any theoretical significance to the constant.

In the following tables detailed results are given for two of the above mentioned mixtures. They are chosen as being typical of the best (Table III) and the worst (Table II) fit obtained with the equation.

* For different temperatures.

TABLE II.

Ethyl alcohol—water (10°).

Percentage by wt. of alcohol.	Density.	η (obs.).	η (calc.).	Percentage Recent equation.	Percentage Spell's equation.	error Macleod's equation.
0	0.99973	0.01308	0.01308	0	0	0
10	0.98393	0.02179	0.01786	18.0	18.1	18.8
20	0.97252	0.03165	0.02648	16.3	14.2	17.8
30	0.95977	0.04050	0.03594	11.2	6.1	8.1
40	0.94238	0.04390	0.04215	4.0	0.2	0
50	0.92162	0.04180	0.04328	3.5	5.2	3.3
60	0.89927	0.03770	0.04087	8.4	7.1	2.6
70	0.87602	0.03268	0.03605	10.3	7.1	0
80	0.85197	0.02710	0.02987	10.2	0.2	3.3
90	0.82654	0.02101	0.02277	8.4	4.4	2.9
100	0.79784	0.01466	0.01466	0	0	0

TABLE III.

Lutidine—ethyl alcohol (25°).

Percentage by wt. of lutidine.	Density.	η (obs.).	η (calc.).	Percentage Present equation.	Percentage Spell's equation.	error Macleod's equation.
0	0.79043	0.011536	0.011536	0	0	0
9.97	0.80382	0.011490	0.011459	0.35	0.77	0.34
19.88	0.81972	0.011643	0.011702	0.51	0.20	0
39.77	0.85142	0.012023	0.011890	1.1	2.02	1.19
59.70	0.88029	0.011328	0.011335	0.06	0.6	0
79.43	0.90743	0.010204	0.010336	1.3	1.23	2.06
90.55	0.92101	0.009686	0.009518	1.74	1.75	1.92
100	0.93218	0.0087766	0.0087766	0	0	0

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